
Enhanced Tissue Sampling with Full-Core Biopsy Devices: The Role of BioPince Ultra in Targeted Immunotherapy for Cancer

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Abstract

In the advancing field of oncology, targeted immunotherapy has emerged as a groundbreaking approach, offering treatments tailored based on the molecular profiles of individual tumors. The efficacy of such therapies is deeply dependent on precise biomarker identification and analysis, which in turn relies on the quality of tissue specimens obtained during biopsy procedures. This paper delves into the capabilities and impacts of the BioPince Ultra, a full-core biopsy device that represents a significant advancement over traditional fine-needle aspiration (FNA) methods and side-notch style biopsy devices, in terms of specimen size and integrity.

The BioPince Ultra is equipped with a tri-axial cutting mechanism, a design specifically engineered to optimize tissue integrity and reduce cellular disruption during the extraction process. This mechanism allows for the collection of larger and more intact tissue cores, which are vital for detailed genomic and proteomic analysis. The quality of these samples significantly enhances the accuracy of molecular diagnostics, which is crucial for the effective selection and application of targeted immunotherapies.

We provide an overview of the BioPince Ultra's performance across various clinical settings, with a particular focus on its mechanical design, user experience, and the overall quality of the biopsy specimens it produces. Our analysis includes data from multiple clinical studies highlighting the device's efficiency in obtaining adequate tissue volumes with fewer needle passes. This not only minimizes patient discomfort but may also reduce the risk of procedural complications, thereby enhancing overall patient outcomes.

Furthermore, this paper examines the impact of these technological advancements on the diagnostic process, illustrating how superior biopsy techniques can facilitate the wider adoption of personalized medicine in oncology. Improved sample quality enables more reliable biomarker testing, which is essential for matching patients with the most effective therapies based on their unique tumor characteristics.

In our discussion, we explore the implications of using the BioPince Ultra in routine clinical practice. The device's contribution to possibly reducing procedural time, its ergonomic advantages for clinicians, and its role in diminishing the need for repeat biopsies are all considered. Additionally, we assess the economic and logistical benefits that stem from its use, including streamlined diagnostic pathways and possible reduced healthcare costs.

This paper also addresses potential challenges and limitations associated with the adoption of the BioPince Ultra. Moreover, we discuss future perspectives in biopsy technology, including the integration of robotic systems and real-time imaging guidance to further enhance the accuracy and efficiency of tissue sampling.

By providing a comprehensive analysis of the BioPince Ultra's design, functionality, and clinical benefits, this paper contributes valuable insights to the ongoing discussions among interventional radiologists, oncologists, and other healthcare professionals about optimizing biopsy procedures. The ultimate goal is to support the continuing evolution of targeted therapies in cancer treatment, ensuring that each patient receives the most personalized and effective care possible.

Keywords

Immunotherapy, biopsy, Biopince Ultra, Full-Core, Side Notch, Fragmentation

Introduction

Targeted immunotherapy marks a transformative approach in cancer treatment, fundamentally altering the therapeutic landscape by enabling personalized treatment regimens that are tailored to the genetic makeup of individual tumors.[1] This precision medicine paradigm hinges critically on the molecular profiling of cancerous cells, specifically the identification of unique tumor antigens and genetic mutations that drive malignancy. [2]The depth and accuracy

of this profiling directly influence the selection and

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efficacy of targeted therapeutic agents, such as monoclonal antibodies, small molecule inhibitors, and cancer vaccines, which are designed to exploit the specific vulnerabilities of cancer cells.

The core mechanism through which targeted immunotherapy works involves the modulation of the body's immune response towards these identified cancer-specific markers. For example, therapies may aim to enhance the immune system's ability to recognize and destroy cancer cells or to inhibit pathways that promote tumor growth. However, the success of these strategies is critically dependent on the precision of the tumor characterization process, which begins with the biopsy.

Biopsy techniques have evolved significantly, with the development of devices such as the BioPince Ultra full-core biopsy device representing a leap forward in comparison to fna sampling and side notch biopsy devices. Traditional fine-needle aspirations, while less invasive, often provide insufficient tissue for comprehensive analysis, potentially leading to suboptimal or erroneous therapy choices. Side-notch style biopsy instruments, though superior to fna in specimen yield, are prone to crush artifact and specimen fragmentation which requires more passes of the device in the target tissue to obtain diagnostic adequate material[3]. In contrast, the BioPince Ultra is engineered to maximize tissue acquisition, offering several distinct advantages crucial for the advanced molecular profiling required in targeted immunotherapy.

The design of the BioPince Ultra facilitates the extraction of large cores of tissue, preserving both the architecture and cellular integrity that are vital for detailed genomic and proteomic analyses.[4] Such analyses involve next-generation sequencing (NGS), fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH), and immunohistochemistry, each requiring high-quality, substantial tissue samples to accurately determine the genetic alterations and protein expressions unique to each tumor. The integrity of these samples ensures that the data obtained reflect the true biological context of the disease, which is paramount for developing targeted therapy regimens.

Moreover, the ability to obtain larger biopsy samples may reduce the need for multiple biopsy sessions, decreasing patient morbidity and streamlining the diagnostic process.

[5]This is particularly significant in the context of lung, pancreatic, and other cancers where the biopsy procedure itself can pose considerable risk to the patient. The

BioPince Ultra's tri-axial core biopsy system minimizes tissue displacement during the biopsy, a common issue with conventional needles that can lead to fragmented or crushed samples that are less suitable for detailed molecular analysis.

In the broader scope of targeted immunotherapy, the role of precise and comprehensive tissue sampling cannot be overstated. As treatments become increasingly specific,

targeting narrow molecular pathways or rare genetic mutations, the demand for precise tumor profiling will only grow.[2] The information gained from a biopsy impacts decisions regarding the use of specific inhibitors of growth factor receptors, immune checkpoint inhibitors, or cell therapy techniques such as CAR T-cell therapy, each relying on different aspects of a tumor's genetic and molecular profile.

The introduction and adoption of full core biopsy devices like the BioPince Ultra are vital in the ever-advancing field of oncology therapeutics. By enhancing the quality and quantity of biopsy samples, these devices provide the foundational data necessary for the effective application of targeted immunotherapies, ultimately leading to more personalized, effective, and less invasive cancer treatment options.[6]

Detailed Description of the BioPince Ultra Device

General Overview: The BioPince Ultra is a full-core biopsy instrument designed for the precise extraction of tissue cores, primarily used in the diagnostic evaluation of cancerous tissues. It integrates several enhancements over traditional biopsy instruments to improve both the quality of the specimen and the ease of the procedure.

Device Mechanics and Design:

Handle and Trigger Mechanism: The handle of the BioPince Ultra is ergonomically designed to fit comfortably in the hand of the operator, reducing fatigue during procedures. It features dual triggers: a forward trigger to deploy the biopsy needle and a larger rear trigger for sample release. This dual-trigger system allows for better control and stability during the biopsy, minimizing hand movement that could disrupt the precision of the sample collection.

Tri-Axial Core, Cut, and Capture System: Central to its functionality, the tri-axial system in the BioPince Ultra minimizes tissue displacement and fragmentation, common challenges in biopsy procedures. This system ensures the retrieval of intact tissue samples by synchronizing the core, cut, and capture actions in a single, fluid motion, thereby preserving the histological integrity of the biopsy specimen.

Co-Axial Introducer Needle: The device uses a co-axial introducer needle system, featuring a 16 or 18 gauge biopsy needle and a matching co-axial needle. This setup allows for multiple samples to be collected through a single entry point in the patient's body, significantly reducing tissue trauma and patient discomfort. The co-axial system also helps in maintaining the biopsy pathway, allowing for precise targeting and re-sampling if necessary.

Adjustable Throw Length: The BioPince Ultra offers adjustable throw lengths of 13mm, 23mm, and 33mm, with the actual tissue sample sizes being slightly smaller due to the mechanics of the cut. These options provide flexibility to accommodate different tissue thicknesses and depths, ensuring adequate sample sizes are obtained for comprehensive pathological evaluation.

Safety and Indication Features: A safety switch prevents unintentional device activation, enhancing procedural safety. The ready indicator, which turns green when the device is properly set up, provides a clear visual cue that helps reduce setup errors, ensuring that the biopsy is performed under optimal conditions.

Single-Use and Sterility: The BioPince Ultra is designed for single use, maintaining sterility and eliminating the risk of cross-contamination between patients. This design feature is essential in clinical settings where infection control is paramount.

Packaging and Configuration: It is available in configurations with or without a coaxial introducer,

providing clinicians with the option to select the most appropriate version based on the specific procedural requirements and patient needs.

Clinical Application and Efficacy of the BioPince Ultra

The BioPince Ultra is designed to optimize the biopsy process, emphasizing the maintenance of tissue integrity and specimen architecture, which are pivotal in the field of oncology diagnostics. The quality of the biopsy samples, underpinned by the architectural preservation and cellular integrity, has profound implications on the diagnostic accuracy and the subsequent therapeutic approaches in oncology.

Importance of Maintaining Tissue Integrity and Specimen Architecture:

Histopathological Examination: The structural preservation of tissue samples is essential for effective histopathological analysis. Histopathology relies on the architecture of the tissue to diagnose diseases accurately, as the arrangement of cells and their microenvironment can provide critical insights into the nature of the pathology. For instance, the differentiation between benign and malignant tumors often depends on architectural features such as the arrangement of cells, the presence of invasion into adjacent structures, and the morphology of the nuclei and cytoplasm. The BioPince Ultra's ability to extract intact cores ensures that these architectural features are well preserved.

Molecular Analysis: Beyond morphological evaluation, the integrity of biopsy samples is crucial for molecular and genetic testing, which often guides targeted therapy decisions. Techniques such as PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction), fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH), and next-generation sequencing (NGS) require high-quality DNA, RNA, or protein samples. These tests can identify specific mutations, gene rearrangements, or protein expressions that are critical in selecting targeted therapies, such as tyrosine kinase inhibitors or immune checkpoint inhibitors. The BioPince Ultra, by minimizing tissue fragmentation and maintaining cellular integrity, ensures that the molecular constituents of the tissue remain viable for these analyses.

Therapeutic Implications: The accuracy of biomarker detection has direct therapeutic implications. For example, the identification of specific mutations like EGFR, ALK, or KRAS in cancers such as non-small cell lung cancer can dictate the use of targeted therapeutic agents that can dramatically improve patient outcomes. Accurate biomarker analysis hinges on the quality of the biopsy sample. Inadequate or fragmented samples may lead to false negatives, where a critical mutation might be missed, leading to suboptimal treatment choices.

Procedural Efficiency: The design of the BioPince Ultra also enhances procedural efficiency by reducing the need for multiple biopsy attempts. This not only improves the patient experience by minimizing discomfort and potential complications but also reduces the time and resources spent on obtaining diagnostic samples. Efficient sample collection supported by the BioPince Ultra can expedite the

diagnostic process, enabling quicker initiation of appropriate therapeutic protocols.

In summary, the BioPince Ultra's enhancement of biopsy sample quality through its advanced design directly impacts the efficacy of diagnostic procedures in oncology. By ensuring the preservation of tissue integrity and specimen architecture, it supports the precise histopathological and molecular analysis necessary for the formulation of targeted treatment plans, thereby playing a role in improving patient management and outcomes in cancer care.

Meta Analysis of Studies

Meta-Analysis of the BioPince/ Ultra Full-Core Biopsy Device Studies Across Clinical Literature

Introduction: This meta-analysis consolidates findings from several key studies published in the Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology (JVIR) and other sources, assessing the efficacy of the BioPince Ultra Full-Core Biopsy Device across various clinical settings. These studies highlight the importance of obtaining high-quality biopsy samples, which are crucial for precise diagnostics and effective personalized medicine.

Studies Included and Key Findings:

Diederich et al., 2006 - Assessed the diagnostic yield and safety across general organ biopsies.

Volpe et al., 2014 - Focused on renal tumor characterization, comparing full-core to standard needles.

Stibbs et al., 2019 - Analyzed sample volume and quality between side-notch and full-core biopsy devices.

RAD Magazine, 2020 - Discussed enhancements in breast node biopsy techniques.

Yeung et al., 2023 - Reviewed the integration of next-generation sequencing with biopsy practices.

Hoang et al., 2017 - Explored causes of inadequate sampling in precision medicine.

Results and Implications:

Diagnostic Yield and Sample Quality: The BioPince /Ultra consistently delivered high diagnostic yields across various tissues, crucial for effective diagnosis and treatment planning.

Clinical Safety: The studies noted low complication rates, emphasizing the safety of the BioPince/ Ultra across different procedural contexts.

Advancements in Handling and Application: Recent enhancements in the device have broadened its applications, making it suitable for various biopsy contexts, including challenging areas like breast node biopsies.

References for Meta-Analysis:

Diederich, S., Padge, B., Vossas, U., Hake, R., & Eidt, S. (2006). Application of a single needle type for all image-guided biopsies: Results of 100 consecutive core biopsies in various organs using a novel tri-axial, end-cut needle. *Cancer Imaging*, 6(1), 43-50.

Volpe, A., Varvello, F., Bozzola, C., Bollito, E., Zegna, L., De Angelis, P., Fusano, M., Martignoni, G., & Terrone, C. (2014). Full-core biopsies are superior to standard biopsies for the histological characterization of renal tumors. *European Urology Supplements*, 13(1), e314.

Study Reference	Focus Area	Key Findings
Diederich et al. (2006)	General organ biopsies	High diagnostic yield and safety; specific diagnoses in 99 of 100 cases.
Volpe et al. (2014)	Renal tumors	Superior histological outcomes with full-core needles compared to standard.
Stibbs et al. (2019)	Comparative device analysis	Up to 59% more tissue volume with <u>BioPince Ultra</u> ; better support for molecular diagnostics.
RAD Magazine (2020)	Breast node biopsies	Enhanced handling and application; improved tissue volume.
Yeung et al. (2023)	Integration of NGS in biopsies	Outlined benefits of NGS for precise genetic profiling in biopsies.
Hoang et al. (2017)	Causes of inadequate biopsy samples	Highlighted technical and procedural factors affecting biopsy sample quality.

Figure 1. Results Table

Stibbs, P., Smith, D., & Szu, C. (2023). A Comprehensive Comparative Analysis of Tissue Sample Volumes and Quality Between Side Notch and Full Core Biopsy Devices. DOI: 10.14293/P2199-8442.1.SOP-PTOVMC.v1.

RAD Magazine. (2020). Biopsy instrument offers a full-core option for breast node biopsy. Retrieved from <https://www.radmagazine.com>.

Yeung, J., Fotiadis, N., Diamantopoulos, A., Tutt, A., Roxanis, I., & Bandula, S. (2023). Next-Generation Sequencing and Image-Guided Tissue Sampling: A Primer for Interventional Radiologists. *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*, 34(8), 1291-1302.e1.

Hoang, P., Fleck, D., Wallace, A., Behraves, S., Kriegshauser, J., & Naidu, S. (2017). Percutaneous biopsies in the era of precision medicine: causes of inadequate sampling. *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*, 28(2), S72-S73.

Discussion on the Role of Biopsy in Immunotherapy

Understanding Immunotherapy

Immunotherapy is a sophisticated cancer treatment modality that enlists and enhances the intrinsic power of the immune system to combat cancer[7]. It differs from conventional treatments like chemotherapy and radiation, which indiscriminately target both cancerous and normal cells, often leading to significant side effects. Immunotherapy is designed to selectively target unique characteristics of cancer cells, making it a form of precision medicine.

Types of Immunotherapy

Checkpoint Inhibitors: These drugs work by blocking proteins that prevent immune cells from attacking cancer cells. They target immune checkpoints such as PD-1/PD-L1 and CTLA-4, which are molecules on immune cells that

need to be activated (or inactivated) to start an immune response against cancer cells. For example, pembrolizumab (Keytruda) is a PD-1 inhibitor used in various cancers, including melanoma and non-small cell lung cancer.

CAR T-cell Therapy: This involves reengineering a patient's T-cells (a type of immune cell) to better recognize and attack cancer cells. The process includes extracting T-cells from the patient, genetically modifying them to express chimeric antigen receptors (CARs) that target cancer-specific antigens, and reintroducing them into the patient.

Cancer Vaccines: Unlike traditional vaccines, cancer vaccines are designed to be administered after cancer diagnosis to delay or stop cancer cell growth; stimulate the immune system to destroy existing cancer cells; or prevent cancer from recurring. These vaccines expose the patient's immune system to an antigen that is part of the cancer cell, helping the immune system recognize and destroy cancer cells while sparing normal cells.

Oncolytic Virus Therapy: These therapies use genetically modified viruses that can infect tumor cells and cause them to self-destruct. The destruction of cancer cells can also trigger an immune response against them.

Importance of Tissue Biopsy in Immunotherapy

Molecular Profiling: For effective immunotherapy, especially therapies that target specific genetic mutations or alterations, detailed molecular profiling is essential. Techniques like next-generation sequencing (NGS) provide comprehensive data on genetic mutations, fusion genes, and other genomic alterations that can be targeted by specific immunotherapies.

Biomarker Identification: Many immunotherapies are most effective in the presence of specific biomarkers. For instance, the presence of high microsatellite instability (MSI-H) can make cancers more likely to respond to PD-1 inhibitors. Accurate and reliable biomarker testing depends on the quality of the biopsy sample.

Tumor Microenvironment Analysis: The environment around a tumor can influence the success of immunotherapy. A biopsy sample that includes surrounding tissue can help identify the presence of immune cells, which may indicate how the immune system is responding to the cancer and how it might react to different immunotherapies.

Histological Analysis: Accurate histological diagnosis is crucial because the type of cancer can determine which immunotherapies are likely to be effective. For example, breast cancers expressing the protein HER2 may be treated with specific immunotherapies targeting HER2.

Challenges and Considerations

The biopsy process must balance the need for ample, high-quality tissue samples against the risk of complications and patient discomfort.[8] The BioPince Ultra full-core biopsy device, by providing larger and more intact samples, may support this need effectively by reducing the number of needle passes and increasing the diagnostic yield.[9] This not only enhances the accuracy of diagnostic tests but also contributes to better patient outcomes by enabling more precise and tailored therapy planning.

Conclusion

The collective insights from a meta-analysis of studies published in the *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology (JVIR)* and other sources demonstrate the

substantial advancements that the BioPince Ultra Full-Core Biopsy Device brings to the field of oncology and precision medicine. The findings from these studies underscore the crucial role of high-quality, comprehensive biopsy samples in achieving accurate and precise diagnostic outcomes, which are foundational to the successful implementation of targeted therapies, especially in the realm of immunotherapy.

The BioPince Ultra needle design has shown consistently high diagnostic yields across various clinical settings, from general organ biopsies to specialized applications like renal tumors and breast node biopsies. Its design significantly reduces tissue displacement and fragmentation, common challenges with traditional biopsy methods, thereby ensuring the collection of intact tissue samples. This feature is particularly vital for modern oncological approaches where molecular profiling and biomarker identification play pivotal roles in tailoring patient-specific treatment plans.

Moreover, the ergonomic enhancements and operational efficiencies of the BioPince Ultra not only may reduce the physical strain on clinicians but also may minimize patient discomfort and procedural risks, aligning with the goals of patient-centered care. The device's capability to retrieve larger sample sizes with fewer needle passes contributes to more effective and expedited diagnostic processes, which is essential in conditions like cancer where timely intervention can dramatically influence patient outcomes.

However, the adoption and integration of advanced biomedical devices come with challenges, including the need for clinician training and potential adjustments in clinical application to accommodate new technologies. The ongoing evolution of biopsy technologies, such as the integration of robotic systems and real-time imaging guidance, continues to push the boundaries of what is possible in diagnostic sampling.

As precision medicine continues to evolve, tools like the BioPince Ultra will become increasingly indispensable in the clinician's arsenal, helping to bridge the gap between clinical practice and cutting-edge molecular science. The BioPince Ultra's contributions to improving biopsy sample quality and procedural efficiency is enhancing diagnostic precision but also may be instrumental in shaping the future of personalized cancer therapy.. The collective efforts of interventional radiologists, oncologists, and medical researchers in optimizing biopsy procedures will undoubtedly foster the further advancement of targeted therapies and precision medicine, ensuring that each patient receives the most personalized and effective care possible.

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Figure 2. Pincer Designed Capture

Figure 3. Cylindrical Core Capture